

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Circular Dichroism in the Multi-Photon Ionization of Oriented Helium Ions

To cite this article: M. Ilchen *et al* 2017 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **875** 022029

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

Related content

- [Multi-photon ionization of lithium](#)
Michael Schuricke, Ganjun Zhu, Jochen Steinmann et al.
- [Angular distribution in multi-photon ionization of hydrogen in intense laser fields](#)
Brant Abeln, Daniel Weflen, Klaus Bartschat et al.
- [Time-dependent theoretical approach to the influence of laser fields on the resonance enhanced multi-photon ionization of SH radical](#)
Yue Da-Guang, Zheng Xiao-Yun, Liu Hao et al.

Circular Dichroism in the Multi-Photon Ionization of Oriented Helium Ions

M. Ilchen^{1,2,*}, N. Douguet³, T. Mazza¹, A. J. Rafipoor¹, C. Callegari⁴, P. Finetti⁴, O. Plekan⁴, K. C. Prince^{4,5,6}, A. Demidovich⁴, C. Grazioli⁴, L. Avaldi⁷, P. Bolognesi⁷, M. Coreno⁷, M. Di Fraia⁸, M. Devetta⁹, Y. Ovcharenko¹, S. Düsterer¹⁰, K. Ueda¹¹, K. Bartschat³, A. N. Grum-Grzhimailo^{1,12}, A. V. Bozhevolnov¹³, A. K. Kazansky^{14,15,16}, N. M. Kabachnik^{1,12,16}, and M. Meyer^{1,*2}

¹ European XFEL GmbH, Holzkoppel 4, 22869 Schenefeld Hamburg, Germany

² PULSE at Stanford, 2575 Sand Hill Road, Menlo Park, 94025 California, USA

³ Department of Physics and Astronomy, Drake University, Des Moines, Iowa 50311, USA

⁴ Elettra-Sincrotrone Trieste, 34149 Basovizza, Italy

⁵ Istituto Officina dei Materiali, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Area Science Park, 34149 Trieste, Italy

⁶ Molecular Model Discovery Laboratory, Department of Chemistry and Biotechnology, Swinburne University of Technology, Melbourne, Victoria 3122, Australia

⁷ CNR Istituto Struttura della Materia, Via del Fosso del Cavaliere, 100-00133 Roma, Italy

⁸ Department of Physics, University of Trieste, 34128 Trieste, Italy

⁹ Istituto di fotonica e nanotecnologie CNR-IFN, Milano, Italy

¹⁰ Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY), Notkestrasse 85, 22603 Hamburg, Germany

¹¹ Institute of Multidisciplinary Research for Advanced Materials, Tohoku University, Sendai 980-8577, Japan

¹² Skobel'syn Institute of Nuclear Physics, Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow 119991, Russia

¹³ Sankt Petersburg State University, Universitetskaya nab. 7/9, Sankt Petersburg 199164, Russia

¹⁴ Departamento de Física de Materiales, UPV/EHU, 25018 San Sebastian/Donostia, Spain

¹⁵ IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, 48011 Bilbao, Spain

¹⁶ Donostia International Physics Center (DIPC), 25018 San Sebastian/Donostia, Spain

Synopsis Intense, circularly polarized extreme-ultraviolet (XUV) and near-infrared (NIR) laser pulses are combined to double-ionize atomic helium via the oriented intermediate $\text{He}^+(3p)$ resonance state. A strong and NIR-intensity dependent circular dichroism is accounted to a helicity dependent AC-Stark shift.

The dichroic interaction of circularly polarized X-rays with matter is a multi-disciplinary field of science. With the advent of circularly polarized free-electron lasers (FELs) [1, 2], the research field of circular dichroism phenomena in non-linear and ultrafast physics has been extended to the soft X-ray regime. Using high intensity, narrow bandwidth XUV pulses from FERMI in Italy with a photon energy of 48.4 eV, we were able to first ionize and subsequently orient ionic helium in the $3p$ ($m=+1$) magnetic substate. From there, the population of this state was controlled by a helicity-dependent AC Stark shift generated by an overlapped near-infrared laser. The measured circular dichroism of electrons emitted via multi-photon ionization of the ionic $3p$ state is intensity dependent to a surprisingly strong extent, therefore allowing for an easily controllable and polarization selective transparency of such resonances [3]. The experimental results depicted in Fig. 1 are in excellent agreement with two independent calculations based on the Time Dependent Schrödinger Equation (TDSE) [4, 5]. Potential applications in the general context of chirality research at FELs will be presented.

Figure 1. Circular dichroism for electrons ejected from the oriented $\text{He}^+(3p)$ state after multi-photon absorption ($E_{kin} \approx 200$ meV) as function of the NIR peak intensity [3].

References

- [1] E. Allaria, *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. X* **4**, 041040 (2014).
- [2] A. A. Lutman, *et al.*, *Nat. Phot.* **10**, 1038 (2016).
- [3] M. Ilchen, *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **118**, 013002 (2017).
- [4] A. K. Kazansky and N. M. Kabachnik *J. Phys. B* **40**, 2163 (2007).
- [5] N. Douguet *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. A* **93**, 033402 (2016).

¹E-mail: markus.ilchen@xfel.eu

²E-mail: michael.meyer@xfel.eu

